

ELECTRICAL CONTROL OF ELASTIC WAVE IN RANDOMLY DISORDERED PHONONIC CRYSTALS BY EXTERNAL PIEZOELECTRIC CIRCUIT

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ABSTRACT

Phononic crystals can show the stop band properties in which the elastic wave and vibration cannot propagate. Because of the mismatch of material and structural characteristics during the practical engineering, disordered defects usually appear and elastic wave localization can be found. This work studies the elastic wave propagation which is controlled by the external piezoelectric circuit. Stop band behaviours and elastic wave localization are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Phononic crystals are periodic composite structures by different materials. They can exhibit the phenomenon of the elastic wave stop band. In recent years, the propagation of elastic waves in periodic structures has received a lot of attention. Because of the stop bands, phononic crystals can be applied to noise and vibration isolation, elastic wave filters, sonic unidirectional transmission, etc. In order to have large stop bands, many studies have been performed to show the formation mechanisms and the tunable methods.

On the other hand, we know that the external piezoelectric circuit combines the merits of both electrical and mechanical systems. They have the electric effect which results in the new elastic dynamic properties. For the piezoelectric composite, the surrounding environment becomes more complicated and the coupling between the mechanical and electrical parameters should be considered. Then, piezoelectric material is introduced into phononic crystals to have the controllable characteristics.

In practical engineering, there are sometimes random defects (e.g. the manufacturing error, the material defects, etc.). The random defects will reduce in the lattice geometry and material constants and elastic wave localization can appear in the disordered phononic crystals. Based on the Lyapunov exponent method, the localization factors can be calculated. This work presents the study of elastic wave localization being controlled by the external piezoelectric circuit.

2 EQUATIONS

Figure 1: Control of elastic wave propagation in phononic crystals with external piezoelectric circuit.

As show in Fig.1, the phononic crystal rod is attached by piezoelectric circuit periodically. In dynamic systems, Lyapunov exponent is defined as the average exponential rate of convergence or divergence between two neighboring phase orbits in the phase space and considered a measure of chaoticity [1–3]. With the method of the Lyapunov exponent, the rate of decay of wave amplitudes of the wave localization in disordered periodic structures can be calculated. For the $2m \times 2m$ transfer matrices, the m pairs of Lyapunov exponents have the following property

$$\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_m \geq 0 \geq \lambda_{m+1} (= -\lambda_m) \geq \lambda_{m+2} (= -\lambda_{m-1}) \geq \dots \geq \lambda_{2m} (= -\lambda_1) \quad (1)$$

For the multi-coupled structures, the smallest positive Lyapunov exponent λ_m is defined as the localization factor which shows the average exponential decay rate of wave amplitudes. It denotes the wave that has the less amount of decay and transmits energy farther along the structure than any other waves. In this work, we apply the algorithm presented by Wolf et al. to calculate the Lyapunov exponents [4]. The formulation for calculating the d th Lyapunov exponent ($1 \leq d \leq 2m$) is expressed as the following form:

$$\lambda_d = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln \left\| \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{3R,d}^{(i+1)} \right\| \quad (2)$$

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REFERENCES

- [1] M.P. Castanier and C. Pierre, Lyapunov exponents and localization phenomena in multi-coupled nearly periodic systems, *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **183**, 1995, pp. 493–515 (doi: [10.1006/jsvi.1995.0267](https://doi.org/10.1006/jsvi.1995.0267)).
- [2] W.C. Xie, Buckling mode localization in rib-stiffened plates with randomly misplaced stiffeners, *Computers and Structures*, **67**, 1998, pp. 175–189 (doi: [10.1016/S0045-7949\(98\)00017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-7949(98)00017-0)).
- [3] F.M. Li and Y.S. Wang, Study on wave localization in disordered periodic layered piezoelectric composite structures, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **42**, 2005, pp. 6457–6474 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2005.03.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2005.03.004)).
- [4] A. Wolf, J.B. Swift, H.L. Swinney and J.A. Vastano, Determining Lyapunov exponents from a time series, *Physica D*, **16**, 1985, 285–317 (doi: [10.1016/0167-2789\(85\)90011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789(85)90011-9)).